

Tracer study on TVET students transiting to employment: A cohort study of The Eldoret National polytechnic department of hospitality and nutrition 2016 graduation class

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Abstract

This is a tracer study of trainees transiting to employment that focuses on post-training evaluation. A trace study is important in explaining the reliability and validity of the various courses offered by TVETs and establishing the relationship between training institutions and the industry. The general objective was to conduct a tracer study on TVET students transiting to employment: a cohort study of the 2016 graduating class of the hospitality and nutrition department. The specific objectives of the study were: to assess the impact of training among 2016 graduating class of Hospitality and nutrition department in The Eldoret National polytechnic, and to establish gaps in training among 2016 graduating class of Hospitality and nutrition department in The Eldoret National polytechnic. The study was guided by change theory, which explains the relevance of human transitions to livelihood living. The study employed a cohort study (longitudinal). The target population was 124 students from the hospitality department's graduating class of 2016. The sample size of the study was 95 respondents. The non-probability sampling technique of snowballing was used to trace the graduates. A structured telephone questionnaire and a few open-ended questions were used to collect data, and descriptive statistics and thematic analysis were employed. The findings showed that TVETs are meeting the standards of the industry, and a significant number of TVET graduates are applying skills learned in college. Furthermore, findings revealed that skills acquired were relevant for employment. But there are gaps in TVETs that require strengthening; a number of trainees are unemployed, a significant few numbers of trainees have acquired new skills in the industry, there have been new food trends, and modernized equipment has also changed industry needs. The study recommends a revision of the curriculum and strengthening of training approaches and procedures to address gaps identified by the tracer study.

Key words: transitions, employment, trainings, industry, TVETs

Introduction

A tracer study or graduate survey is a standardized survey (in written or oral form) of graduates from educational institutions that takes place sometime after graduation or the end of the training. The subjects of a tracer study can be manifold, but common topics include questions on study progress, the transition to work, work entrance, job career, use of learned competencies, current occupation, and bonds to the education institution (school, center, university). The objectives of tracer studies are very different, but some common elements can be identified. Some tracer studies produce only simple descriptive findings about the employment situation of graduates, while others try to explain the employment situation by analyzing the links between employment and education (Smith, 2009).

Tracer studies of individual TVET institutions or individual study programs in the TVET institution can produce valuable information for a broad range of actions and functions of TVET institutions. A tracer study should: be valuable for a broad range of stakeholders; cover a broad range of aspects of employment and work; give some explanations of the causes of professional success and employment outcomes; and analyze the impact of various features of education to gain empirically based hints for improvement. The tracer study should be designed in a way that ensures feedback that is motivating and valuable for considering improvements in TVET and higher education institutions (Singo & da Costa, 2017).

It is now apparent that the “TVET” Sector is expected to play a very significant role with regards to the Country’s education and training system in contributing to economic growth and meeting Kenyan government agenda on the Big four. The Government considers it as one of the important tools for economic prosperity, and that of employment creation. The Ministry of Higher Education, Research, Science, and Technology through the state ministry of vocational education are now expected to embark on serious advocacy and state funding to address the needs of TVET and ensure its relevance to labour market needs (Smith, 2009).

The Kenyan economic reports indicate that over 50 percent of the population is under the age of 25 years. The youth population is seriously affected by poverty and high unemployment rates. The main policy related issues are an uncoordinated policy and institutional framework for youth development, inadequate vocational and skills training facilities, the persistent growth in unemployment among high school leavers, dropouts, and underutilization of youth talents,

resulting in youth energies being channeled into antisocial activities. The reported issues have led to the major need of addressing youth unemployment by increasing competency trainings to meet the industry needs (Fufa, 2018).

From the evaluation of the national development policies and interventions by the Government through its ministries and state organs, it is clear that the initiatives have not led to the development of a curriculum. The curriculum in TVET institutions by the KICD is made relevant and of high quality to match the job market and the employment opportunities that exist including self-employment, and eventually help to reduce poverty (TEVETA, 2018).

Research problem

The government of Kenya has long recognized the need for a trained workforce, particularly one that possesses technological and vocational skills. In its endeavor to address the problem of youth unemployment, it has initiated in recent years many policies and strategies to address the situation of early school leavers and an untrained and unskilled labor force. It is important for various TVET institution management to explain the transition levels, explain the reliability and validity of the various courses offered by the learning training institutions, and establish the relationship between training institutions and the industry by finding out the extent to which courses fit the needs of society.

Research objective

The general objective was to conduct tracing studies on transition levels of TVET graduating students to employment: a cohort study of 2016 graduating class of Hospitality and nutrition department in The Eldoret National polytechnic.

The specific objectives of the study were:

- i. To assess the impact of training among 2016 graduating class of Hospitality and nutrition department in The Eldoret National polytechnic.
- ii. To establish gaps in training among 2016 graduating class of Hospitality and nutrition department in The Eldoret National polytechnic.

Significance of the study: This study was aimed to achieve the following from the findings obtained: the findings would first reveal the adequacy of the training programmes to meet

industry training needs. Secondly, the study would enable training institutions and industry players to assess the performance of graduates and employees respectively. Thirdly, the study findings aid in identifying gaps in training, and makes further recommendations for future strengthening of TVETs institutions training programmes to meet industry needs.

Literature review

In many countries, conducting tracer studies is a formal requirement for the accreditation of study programmes. Programmes/projects seeking reform of TVET, which try to improve skills match and the transition from school to work, use data from tracer studies to measure their effectiveness. Education institutions are also increasingly interested in feedback from their former students to improve their study programmes, and to show new applicants how their graduates have managed the transition to employment (Gamble, 2016). Graduates are usually invited to provide feedback about their experiences on the labour market one to two years after graduation. The information required from the graduates commonly includes: duration of search for the first job, methods of job search, employment status at the time of the survey about one to two years after graduation, and income level. Others include information on the working time, type of contract, job title, economic sector (private or public), economic branch, required knowledge, and skills (competencies), relationships between study and work (horizontal and vertical match), further education and training, regional and international mobility, and personal background characteristics (Fufa, 2018).

Most regular tracer studies in higher education are conducted between one year and three years after graduation (Costa Rica, France, Germany, Hungary, Indonesia, Italy, and Switzerland). The 'first destination surveys' in the UK and Australia are exceptional, being conducted about six months after graduation. There are different considerations in deciding the best time after graduation for the study. Six months after graduation may be considered too early, but it can also be argued that a tracer study should be done only a few months after graduation because this provides rapid feedback and the graduates are easier to contact. Both arguments can be supported but can also be criticized in relation to the objectives of the tracer study. If the results are to be helpful in improving study programmes it is necessary for most graduates to have managed the transition to employment and had some relevant work experience. In poor labour market

conditions it makes no sense to conduct the survey too early when most graduates are still looking for their first job (Rauner, 2009).

Use of tracer studies: Tracer studies are widespread in higher education but also often employed in the TVET (Technical vocational education and training). In many countries, conducting tracer studies is a formal requirement for the accreditation of study programmes

. which try to improve skills match and the transition from school to work, use data from tracer. Education institutions are also increasingly interested in feedback from their former students to improve their study programmes, and to show new applicants how their graduates have managed the transition to employment (Singo & da Costa, 2017).

Tracer studies are not limited to simple descriptive information about the labour market success (the whereabouts) of the graduates. Results of tracer studies provide insights and contributions to explain the labour market situation of the graduates, and stakeholders and users are interested in which elements of the study conditions and provisions have effects on the employment outcomes. Context variables, such as the economic situation, the regional labour market and individual mobility and motivation, need to be taken into account to avoid misinterpretation of results (Smith, 2009).

Bottom-up partnership approaches have been useful in encouraging education institutions to engage in developing tracer study approaches that are tailored to local conditions with limited resources, such as in the TVET sector. Building local initiatives into wider networks, combined with elements of technical methodological support, can spark highly motivated involvement from education institutions in tracer studies aimed at systematic analysis for self-improvement, and based on high standards of implementation of the research. Mutual trust among stakeholders is once more essential in growing such initiatives, and in freeing them from manipulation (Gamble, 2016).

Examples of tracer studies: In Morocco Since 1987, the TVET Department annually carries out tracer studies of TVET graduates to capture a picture of their paths, nine months after graduation. To complete the analysis, the department periodically implements another survey targeted at collecting detailed information from specific cohorts on developments over a period of three years. In Netherlands it is known as the regular school leaver surveys, ‘The school leaver

surveys are designed to function as a monitoring instrument for the transition from school to work, covering the full breadth of the Dutch education system. The statistics generated by these surveys contain information on labour market outcomes, competencies, and subsequent study activities (Ayonmike, 2014).

The ILO has been conducting nationally representative school-to-work transition surveys (SWTSs) in developing and middle-income economies (28 target countries in total). The Work4Youth project is a five-year partnership between the ILO and the MasterCard Foundation. The project field of intervention is data collection and analysis oriented towards policy formulation. The main research focus of Work4Youth is the transitions of young people to the labour market. Evidence on the transition is collected through two rounds of school-to-work transition surveys (SWTSs) run in 28 target countries. The data produced are perfectly comparable across countries and allow for the calculation of benchmarks, as well as for regional and global analyses (Gamble, 2016).

Many European countries have regular tracer studies: either annually in the Netherlands, Switzerland, the UK, or Italy or every three or four years the higher education information system (HIS) in Germany. Some TVET tracer studies are conducted annually, for example in the Philippines by the Technical Education and Skills Development Authority (TESDA), in Morocco by the Department de la Formation Profession Nelle, and in the Netherlands by the Research Centre for Education and the Labour Market (ROA), a research institute of Maastricht University (Rauner, 2009).

Methodology of the study

According to Co-opers (2012) research design represents the framework that will guide the study methodology. The study did employ cohort studies in the aim of achieving the study objectives. The design is appropriate because it handles situations that have occurred of a same population characteristics. The target population of the study represents units, and persons to be studied (Kothari, 2010). The target population of the study was 124 students from hospitality department graduating class of 2016. The sample size of the study was 92 respondents obtained using krejcie & Morgan table. Non-probability sampling technique of snow balling was used to trace the graduates until the sample size is reached from the target population. Structured telephone

interview schedule and open ended questions were used to collect data from the respondents this is after the instruments have been tested for reliability and validity. Descriptive statistics of mean, standard deviation, percentages and frequencies and was used to analyze data aided with SPSS computerized package version 21. Thematic analysis was used to analyze qualitative data from the open ended questions and presented into logical statements.

Findings

The study sample size was 92 graduates, of whom 76 were interviewed successfully; this represented a response rate of 82.6%. According to Kothari (2010), this was adequate for the study to be conducted. Table 1 shows a summary of the general information provided by the respondents.

Table 1 General information

Item survey	Responses	Frequency (n=76)	%
Gender	Male	42	55.3
	Female	34	44.7
Level of the course	Certificate	27	35.5
	Diploma	49	64.5
Course category	Nutrition & dietetics	29	38.2
	Food beverage, Catering & accommodation	47	61.8

The general information shows that 55.3% of the respondents were male and 44.7% were female. Also, the study revealed that 64.5% of the respondents graduated with a diploma course, while 35.5% graduated with a certificate course. Among the graduates, 38.2% did take a nutrition and dietetics course, while 61.8% took either a food and beverage or catering and accommodation course.

Information on employment: The study sought information on the employment status of the respondents; therefore, they were asked questions: if they were already employed, if not, why,

which industries are they employed in, and why they sought a different industry for employment. Findings are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2 Information on employment

Questions	Response	Frequency	%
Are you employed?	Yes	52	68.4
	No	24	31.6
	Total	100	76
Reasons for being unemployed	Cannot find work	19	79.2
	Went back to school	4	16.7
	I am volunteering	1	4.1
	Total	24	100
In which industry are you employed?	Hospitality & catering	30	57.7
	Health industry	9	17.3
	Other industries	8	15.4
	Self-employed	5	9.6
	Totals	52	100
Why are you employed in a different industry of your specialty?	I did not find job in my area of specialty	21	40.4
	The jobs are paying well	14	26.9
	I got a reference and opportunity	9	17.3
	It is our family business	8	15.4
	Totals	52	100

The findings in Table 2 show that 52 (68.4%) of the respondents have been employed, while 24 (31.6%) are not employed. For those not employed, the reasons were: 19 (79.2%) could not find work, 4 (16.7%) went back to school and 1 (4.1%) was volunteering. Furthermore, the study revealed that 30 (57.7%) are employed in hospitality and catering, 9 (17.3%) are employed in the health industry, 8 (15.4%) are employed in other industries, and 5 (9.6%) are self-employed. The reasons for employment in a different industry from their specialty were: 21 (40.4%) did not find a job in the area of specialty; 14 (26.9%) did find jobs from other industries well paying; 9 (17.3%) got a reference and opportunity to work in a different industry; and 8 (15.4%) respondents are working at the family business. These findings reveal that the majority of the respondents are employed and working within their area of specialty. On the other hand, the majority of the unemployed are unable to find work.

Information on skills and industry: This section was aimed at finding out whether the TVET graduates are applying the skills they trained in, whether the skills are relevant, if they added more skills through other trainings, and if TVET is meeting standards in the industry. The findings of these questions are presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Information on skills and industry

Questions	Response	F (n=52)	% (100)
In the hospitality and health industry are you applying the skills you trained in	Yes	31	59.6
	No	21	40.4
Were the skills you acquired in college relevant for employment?	Yes	29	55.8
	No	23	44.2
Have you attended any form of trainings after college?	Yes	22	42.3
	No	30	57.7
Is TVETs meeting the standards of the industry?	Yes	32	61.5
	No	20	38.5

The findings in Table 3 showed that 56.6% of the respondents employed are applying the skills they acquired in college, while 40.4% of them are not. Further, the study revealed that 55.8% of the respondents found the skills acquired in college relevant for employment, while 44.2% of the respondents did not. Slightly more of the respondents (57.7%) have not attended any form of training in college, while 42.3% have not attended any form of training. For those who have attended, they qualitatively mentioned the following trainings: barrister, feeding the sick, counseling, leadership, new cooking methods, a blueprint for establishment preparation, anthropometric tests, and diet planning. Lastly, the study found that 61.5% of respondents agreed that TVETs are meeting the standards of the industry, while 38.5% disagreed that they are not. Based on the findings, it appears that slightly more skills are relevant to the industry, and the TVETs are slightly better at meeting industry needs.

Qualitative findings: The respondents were asked to state qualitatively some of the new things they encountered in the changing work industry. They mentioned the following: there is a focus on eating healthy; individuals are going back to traditional cuisines, e.g., Indian, Japanese, international, and local dishes; there is a change in equipment in the industry; there are new

cooking methods aimed at cutting costs through shortcuts; event planning is prevalent; and there are challenges in handling different types of customers, e.g., languages, disabilities, and personalities.

The respondents were asked qualitatively if they had attended any further training after college. They mentioned the following: they went back to school for a degree course; they went for a teacher training course; they attended short courses such as refresher/health/hazard analysis and critical control points (HACCP); fire aid; and they changed careers to be cabin crew. The respondents were further asked to state some of the skills they acquired in the industry. They qualitatively mentioned the following: barrister, leadership skills such as being a supervisor, and learning new cooking methods. Other examples include the development of blueprints for establishments and producing foods for all seasons.

Conclusion

The tracer study revealed that TVETs are slightly meeting the skills and the standards of the industry and that higher numbers of graduates are employed within their area of specialty. But to increase the percentage of employment and absorption, there are still gaps that need to be filled to strengthen TVETs so that they are able to meet industry needs in the changing world of work. These include changes in curriculum, the adoption of new equipment, and an emphasis on healthy food production techniques and procedures.

Recommendations

The study recommends a number of policy decisions that need to be implemented by the relevant authorities. There is a need to revise the curriculum to emphasize healthy foods, short trainings, and skills such as hazard analysis, leadership, and critical control points (HACCP). The management of TVETs should focus on modernizing the equipment and ways of handling different types of customers. Trainers in TVETs need to embrace new cooking methods focusing on traditional cuisines and minimizing the loss of nutrients.

Future suggestions

There is a need for future studies to be conducted to fill the gaps in the current study. Such as widening the scope of the study to cover all the 2016 graduates and conducting a study to establish the reasons for joining teacher trainer colleges in larger numbers among TVET graduates.

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